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A Study of Couples' behaviour During the State-regulated COVID-19 Lockdown in a South Asian Country

ABSTRACT

Aims:

When assessing the ill-effects this pandemic has brought to humans, one of the most important factors is the psychological influence it has caused on married couples. The study is designed to understand whether they suffer from fears of financial situation/uncertainty and the role of resource availability on the level of adjustment of spouses.

Objective: The objectives of this study were to identify whether individuals suffer from fears of financial situation and uncertainty, to analyse the level of adjustment of spouses, to investigate the resources available for spouses, and to understand whether resource availability moderates the relationship between individuals' fears on financial situation/uncertainty and the level of adjustment of spouses. **Methods:** An online survey was conducted among a chosen random sample and data were collected from 301 participants who were adults 25 years or older, residing in the Western Province of Sri Lanka. Statistical analysis was performed to identify the moderator effect of resources available for spouses. **Results:** The results showed that COVID-19 created uncertainty and fear of financial situation among married couples and, it was concluded that cultural beliefs and support extended from their respective families contributed to the adjustment of Sri Lankan spouses, who managed to remain in stable relationships during the global crisis as a result. **Conclusion:** The study concluded the support extended from the families and cultural beliefs contributed significantly to the adjustment of spouses who managed to stay strong during the global crisis.

Key Words: *COVID-19, Adjustment, Spouses, Uncertainty, Financial Situation, Pandemic.*

I. INTRODUCTION

At the time this article is written, there were already more than 184 million confirmed cases of the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) with 3.97 million Deaths (World Health Organization). COVID-19 was identified in all around the world as an infectious disease which is fatal for many. As one of the largest and fast-spreading health crisis seen in this century, COVID-19 pandemic has brought many deaths as well as many health, safety and socioeconomic challenges to Sri Lanka. When assessing the ill-effects this pandemic has brought to humans, one of the most important factors is the psychological influence it has caused, which includes isolation and uncertainty among people.

The COVID-19 pandemic believed to have intensely altered the daily lives of the people and created multiple challenges in the society. One of such important challenges can be identified as harmonizing intimate relationships of married couples. This is most certainly in relation with emotional as well as physical health. Studies conducted on intimate relationships have proven how external stressors such as financial hardship, stressful jobs, and natural or health disasters may minimise the quality and stability of the relationship of a married couple.

With government regulations requesting social isolation with the COVID-19 lockdown, many people faced significant psychological consequences. The changes that took place in daily routine lives,

feeling lonely, losing jobs, facing financial hardship, and misery over the sicknesses and death of loved ones of COVID-19, may most certainly affect the mental health of people. This has caused the fear of uncertainty among all. When the situation is clearly uncertain, it is important that accurate information is provided about the issue in hand and ways of how to manage it.

The challenges of financial situation and economic insecurity are a serious threat to the well-being of married couples that was brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. The consequences of these challenges will most likely be long-lasting because of the ways family systems function. With the intention of providing such accurate information, the objectives derived for this study are stated as below.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To identify whether individuals suffer from fears on financial situation and uncertainty.
- To analyse the level of adjustment of spouses.
- To investigate the resources available for spouses.
- To understand whether resource availability moderates the relationship between individuals' fears on financial situation/uncertainty and the level of adjustment of spouses.

This article draws from relevant literature across similar topics to identify the different ways of how the harmony of married couples may be threatened during COVID-19. The conceptual framework was created based up on models of various human behaviour and methods these families would function.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Adjustment of Spouses

According to Kendrick and Drentea (2016) Adjustment of Spouses is considered as “the accommodation of spouses to each other”. They further reiterate that aspects which influence such adjustment of spouses include “marital satisfaction, cohesion, agreement, affection, and conflict”. They further point out that “well-adjusted couples are expected to have long-lasting, stable marriages”, while “poorly adjusted marriages are expected to experience instability and even end in divorce”. Adjustment of Spouses may take a long period of time especially at the beginning of the marriage. Also there is a possibility of people changing their thought, attitudes and beliefs which again lead to misunderstandings and conflicts among couples. Adjustment of Spouses, therefore, requires understanding and maturity of couples so they can grow in the marriage. If such growth is not seen then, it will lead to an unsuccessful marital relationship.

Happiness, joy, satisfaction, and fulfilment of expectations can be achieved by married couples if mutual adjustment is there. Carl Rogers (1972, p.243) views the “concept of marriage as the basis of many marital adjustments”.

People experiencing pandemics like COVID-19 must adjust in dealing with practical problems that encounter from the crisis as well as the mental distress it may cause (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). According to Meyerowitz (1983), “people experience high levels of psychological distress” at such times. Research has proven that “distress is positively associated with enacted support” (e.g., Hobfoll & Lerman, 1988; Revenson & Majerowitz, 1990) while many studies prove how distress causes a negative effect on relationships of married couples (Lef-court, Martin, & Saleh, 1984). Married couples usually “jointly decide how much time to devote to daily chores and their children”, which is subject to “their income, social norms, productivity differences in time inputs, and bargaining power” (Schoonbroodt 2018). All schools, day-care centres and kindergartens were closed due to COVID19 and therefore the children needed to be looked after at home. In married couples, the chores of the children and house work can be shared. However, in a single-parent household, the responsibility lies upon that one parent, unless there is another adult person in the house like a grandparent, aunt, or older sibling who can help, since with social distancing outsiders cannot come.

Usually mothers allocate more of their time for child caring than fathers in married couples who are dual-earners. Aguiar, Hurst, and Karabarbounis (2013) claim that “during the Great Recession, men reallocated more time to child care” with the sudden splurge in unemployment everywhere, “while women increased their housework time”. Pabilonia and Vernon (2020, p.9) states that, “when working remotely, fathers shift some of the reduction in their commute time to primary child care, while there is no change in primary child care time for mothers. Some of that increase in time during typical working hours”. Therefore, we can clearly observe from former studies how reducing work activities will encourage men to be more involved in home chores and looking after the children.

When a couple equally understand and agree upon the concept of marriage and responsibilities attached to it, it is easy to live in harmony. However, if there are significant differences in the way they perceive things, conflicts may encounter. Many couples find that when they start living under the same roof for lengthy periods, many differences are found in terms of their values, attitudes, and beliefs especially with the financial uncertainties that they encounter due to COVID-19.

Many research studies have identified how couples who lack financial resources or face financial issues communicate with each other to resolve their differences and adjust to have harmony. Hence it can be seen how financial issues in couples which cause uncertainties among couples can be resolved with adjustment of couples. Married couples, who communicate frequently regarding such financial issues, adjust their own selves to be a good spouse to the other. In the following sections variables of uncertainty, financial situation and resources available for spouses are reviewed in relation to the adjustment of spouses and propose our hypotheses of the study. The conceptual model developed for the study is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Uncertainty

“As a result of this pandemic, people found themselves forced to cope with new emotional challenges and particularly with feelings of stress, uncertainty and fear. Indeed, previous research on viruses shows that pandemic situations exert an emotional impact on people’s levels of uncertainty” (Cohan et al., 2009, p. 513). When people fear for themselves or the health and safety of their loved ones it could cause a psychological impact. When a person feels fear or uncertainty it could generate mental pressure and stress. “During a flu outbreak, about 10–30% of the general public reported major fears of contracting the disease” (Cohan et al., 2009, p.514).

COVID-19 has created many external stressors which contribute to disrupting the functions of ordinary married couples. Even if it is hard to identify the exact impact COVID-19 pandemic brought up on the relationship functioning of married couples, a recent study by American Psychological Association (2020) claims that “many individuals in the United States are experiencing heightened levels of stress as a result of the pandemic, which are closely tied to economic uncertainty and employment concerns”. “Mental health experts also expect an increase in mental health issues, including uncertainty, anxiety, self-harm, and suicide” (Holmes et al., 2020, p.552) as a result of this pandemic. According to Karney, Story, & Bradbury (2005, p.18) it is important to “understand how the current pandemic may impact couples’ relationships” since “couples’ relationship functioning is closely connected to disruptions in economic, employment, and health sectors”. Pietromonaco & Collins (2017) point out that when married couples experience harmony in their relationship and express understanding towards the needs of each other, then it becomes easier to face the current pandemic crisis. Many married couples around the world have stated that COVID-19 pandemic is indeed the very such experience they have had in terms of stress, uncertainty and disruption they go through. COVID-19 pandemic will most likely test all these couples of the strength of their marital bond. Especially the uncertainty associated with the final outcome of the pandemic.

“COVID-19 type of pandemic related stressors which are accompanied by considerable uncertainty, makes it hard to know which impacts may be time limited and which will be longer term” (Karney et al., 2005, p.27). When a married couple is in a harmonious relationship they tend to understand

the needs and necessities of the other person (Reis, Clark, & Holmes, 2004) but “external stressors, such as uncertainty, unemployment, economic hardship, and work stress, can spill over to affect the quality of couples’ interactions and perceptions of the relationship and partner” (Neff & Karney, 2004, p. 143). In such situations these external stresses may make a partner be less responsive to the other. Barton and Lavner (2018, p.189) states that in such circumstances “individuals are more likely to be overly critical or argumentative, blame their partner, provide poorer support and, over time, become less satisfied with their partner and relationship”.

A major source of fear in COVID-19 pandemic was the uncertainty of a person you loved getting infected or even killed. In order to address this fear issue, the society needs to be educated about all relevant information with regard to the pandemic and the precautions they should follow. The biggest fear people face is, not knowing the end of the pandemic. The true mortality numbers, the daily infected number of COVID 19 patients and the different variants are the key concerns people fear. Thus, one has to search the history to find similar situations to get a clearer picture. Among such incidents in history, “considering the set of historical pandemics and epidemics, the 1918 influenza pandemic is the most recent historical event to match or exceed the scale of the COVID-19 pandemic” (Neff & Karney, 2017, p. 149).

This research study shall investigate how uncertainty can play a key role in affecting the harmony, psychological and physical well-being of a marital couples’ relationship during COVID-19 and how it could threaten the normal adjustment these couples would otherwise exercise. Based on the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H1: Uncertainty influences the adjustment of spouses.

Financial Situation of Spouses

With the financial difficulties, economic challenges and social disturbances the COVID-19 pandemic has brought about many disruptions to the relationships of married couples. With the closing down of many businesses due to COVID-19 the unemployment rate has risen and the economy is a downfall which brings many families in to a financial crisis. “During times of widespread economic upheaval, financial stress impacts families directly via individual job loss, as well as indirectly through uncertainty about the national economy and/or local unemployment rates” (Schneider et al., 2017,p.4). Especially for day-wage earners and low income families the existing difficulties are multiplied with the COVID-19 crisis which puts an additional burden to their marital relationships.

The survival of the relationship will depend upon the way they can handle these economic and financial challenges caused as a result of COVID-19. A support system needs to be implemented in each married couple to face the stress factors and survive with the COVID-19 pandemic. These types of financial burdens “may be heightened when parents are managing children with special needs with the reduction in

supports that are likely occurring during the pandemic” (Raphael, Zhang, Liu, & Giardino, 2010, p.219). “Though financial stress and fears of unemployment may be a common experience during the pandemic, the consequences to families may be greater for those with pre existing economic hardship, compared to less economically vulnerable families” (Millet et al., 2020, p.39).

Many studies have analysed the survival methods of various couples during these stressful times. “A study of 451 married couples showed that economic strain such as not enough money to pay expenses was associated with greater emotional distress, which, in turn, was associated with greater marital conflict and marital distress; however, the link between economic strain and emotional distress was weaker for couples who displayed higher quality support” (Conger, Rueter, & Elder, 1999, p.58). Another study done of “multinational 3,000 individuals in romantic relationships also suggest that COVID-19 stressors such as financial strain, social isolation and perceived stress are associated with poorer relationship functioning” (Balzarini et al., 2020, p.12). Susanne Choi (Hutchinson, 2020) a sociologist at the Chinese University of Hong Kong observes how COVID-19 has created many conflicts in married couples as they are confined to periods of lockdown with no social interactions with others. She says that “now forced to live on top of each other, with financial hardships, worries about health, educating children—just getting groceries can trigger many to regress. Without a doubt, the current pressures can bring many issues to the surface, and for some couples, this COVID-19 lockdown will force them to look at their marriage earlier than they may have wanted to. For many, this will be a turning point—surviving together—striving together” (Hutchinson, 2020, p.2).

Financial reasons can be seen as one of the most common factors for divorce in couples (Amato & Rogers, 1997). Therefore, with the financial challenges caused by COVID-19 the marital relationships will most certainly face turbulences and conflicts. In the USA, COVID-19 has created many financial stressors for families. This included “financial difficulties due to a 10.2% unemployment rate and sickness and fear of financial loss” (U.S. Department of Labor, 2020). In Australia “in dual-earner homes, paid work time was slightly lower, and unpaid time was higher during quarantine” (Craig & Churchill, 2020, p.69). Many Fathers have admitted to contributing much more towards household chores and child care during COVID-19 compared to before, due to their unemployment which they acknowledge as a cause for dissatisfaction with their work–family balance. Based on the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H2: Financial situation of spouses influences the adjustment of spouses.

Resources available for spouses

With the COVID-19 government closed all schools and preschools and as a result all the children were stuck at home. The parents were either working from home or were out of their business or lost their jobs. This was a significant disruption to the daily routine of families all around the world. The situation becomes

even challenging when a family member is diagnosed as infected with the COVID-19. However, “the extent to which this severe adversity will impact individual families and children will largely depend on other related factors in their lives” (Doom & Cicchetti, 2018, p.1446). These other related factors include the resources available for the spouses which would enable a married couple to become more tolerable to deal with COVID-19.

One such resource that supports the couples to sustain during COVID-19 is cultural beliefs of what marriage is considered as. COVID-19 has opened eyes of many married couples who may question whether they should have spent more quality time with each other prior to the crisis. The pandemic has forced the couples to spend time with each other which ensures that they devote time to build family beliefs. This in turn diminishes the uncertainty they have due to COVID. “It has also provided a chance for families to reconsider the ratio of togetherness and autonomy going forward” (Fraenkel & Cho, 2020, p.859). When a family member gets infected with COVID-19 many additional stresses fall upon the relationships. Married couples who demonstrate harmonious relationships with their cultural beliefs and background will understand the pressure caused by COVID-19 and will most certainly outdo the crisis and uncertainty. However, “couples who have difficulty communicating and effectively supporting each other may feel less happy with their marriage and possibly be more likely to separate or divorce” (Neff & Karney, 2017, p.140).

Family beliefs and the support extended from the other partner of the marital relationship bring emotional security and stability to fight with the crisis of COVID-19. Such strong and supportive couples would be a pillar of support to their children and even other relatives. Such parents can enable “children with connection and growth during these emotionally difficult times, helping them to not only cope with uncertainty but also to thrive alongside their family members” (Walsh, 2015, p.4). COVID-19 pandemic has created new daily routines for all married couples. The ones who work from home have found ways to balance their work while making time for daily chores and child care. Many parents divide their time and have found new ways of coping with the stressful pandemic and uncertainty associated with it while attending to their duties and responsibilities. According to Fraenkel (2019, p.573) when facing a crisis like COVID-19 “couples and families need to reflect on their higher and broader cultural values—whether derived from spirituality, religion, moral philosophy, or other sources of ethics”.

Walsh (2009, p.3) states “cultural values form spirituality which is a powerful dimension of human experience involving transcendent beliefs and practices that foster meaning, well-being, and connectedness”. Lord Buddha has preached of facing unknown and uncontrollable conditions with mindfulness. Meditation and creating awareness of your mind had been preached as the start of obtaining a peaceful mind. While following the advice given by health professionals and scientists it is also advisable to understand and implement religious and cultural beliefs and methods to fight off feelings of uncertainty. As stated by the great Greek philosopher Aristotle ‘man is a social animal’ and thus the humans long for

associations and regular interactions of other members of the society. Isolation due to lock downs or travel restrictions is a major obstacle for people of all backgrounds in the society. With the cultural requirements such as the expectation of having to attend weddings, funerals and religious gatherings many families faces relationship conflicts with one member wanting to follow regulations while the other prefers to attend such events. However, it can be seen that nowadays people tend to stay home more often and practice social distancing as a choice. More people are avoiding social relations, no longer by imposition, but as a choice. This may affect the cultural practices and interpersonal relationships and bring new trends to fight off uncertainties the couples go through. Based on the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H3: Resources available for spouses moderates the relationship between uncertainty and the adjustment of spouses.

Another resource for adjustment of spouses can be seen as the support from family and relatives. Due to social distancing many close relatives cannot provide support to their families like how they would prior to COVID-19. Many would use electronic modes of communication and social media to keep in touch which includes paying bills online and lending money to help relatives with electronic transactions. Walsh (2015, p.2) states that, “families construct a characteristic system of family beliefs that guides how they survive the financial hardship”. The challenges brought by COVID-19 pandemic, has caused families to build a meaningful systems that would get them through the financial crisis. Falicov et al. (2020, p.872) find that “families that are under-resourced can be more adaptive in coping with the pandemic as they are used to enduring different challenges in life related to poverty, crowding, and confinement problems, compared to well-resourced families”. Imber-Black (2020, p.916) states that, “reinventing old rituals or creating new routines through the use of technology is an opportunity for families to come together through the financial issues”. Such family support mentally and monetarily will indeed help the couples adjust and sustain the financial crisis faced due to COVID-19. Based on the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H4: Resources available for spouses moderates the relationship between financial situation and the adjustment of spouses.

With the above literature review, it can be seen that the resources available for married spouses that affect their adjustment during COVID-19 includes family resources and cultural beliefs.

IV. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Measures

To measure the Fear of Financial situation and Uncertainty, a 14-item measure was used, which can be seen in Appendix 1. These measures were taken using the questionnaire by Deguglielmo (1973), named ‘The

Development of an Instrument for Measuring Financial Adjustment. These items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from always (1) to never (5).

To measure the Adjustment of spouses, a 2-item measure was used, which is shown in Appendix 2. These measures were taken using the questionnaire by Hansen (1978), named 'Marital adjustment, idealization, and conventionalization'. These items are on a four-point Likert-type scale ranging from always agree (4) to disagree frequently (1).

To measure the Resources available for spouses, a 11-item measure was used, which are shown in Appendix 3. These measures were taken using the questionnaire by Deguglielmo (1973), named 'The Development of an Instrument for Measuring Financial Adjustment. These items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from always (1) to never (5).

Population, Sample, and Participants

At the time this is been written the population of Sri Lanka is 21,413,249 (21.41 million) people. Around 42.6% of the population falls in to the age bracket of 25-54 year olds while 6.1% of the country's population is in the 54-60-year age bracket (worldpopulationreview.com 14/08/21). Therefore, we can safely assume that the total number of 25-60 year olds in the whole country are roughly 10 million people. The total number of people in the Western Province comes to 1,973,522 (1.9 million) people out of which total 25-60 year olds are roughly 959,131. In order to get a 95% confidence level with only a 5% chance of the sample results differing from the true population average, confidence interval of the margin of error is calculated by $1/\sqrt{N}$. Here N is considered as the number of participants or sample size (Niles, 2006). Thus, the 300+ participants in the survey were sufficient to justify the total population we survey. The data were collected from 301 respondents. The participants constitute males and females of age 25-60 residing in the Western Province. The average time taken by a participant to complete the survey was 26 minutes. The survey was structured in the English language, which is one of the national languages of the country, and the participants were provided with an introduction about the purpose of the survey before sending the link to the survey. Their participation was voluntary and anonymous.

Method of data collection

In order to fully capture these aspects, the survey questionnaire was prepared. The online survey was conducted from 12th March to 12th June 2021. During this time Sri Lanka had a partial lockdown with inter-district travel restrictions and minimal in person reporting to work. All schools and pre-schools were fully closed and most of the employees worked from home. Once the questionnaire was finalised it was uploaded on google forms and the link was created. Initially, target groups were identified who fall in to the required demographics. Accordingly, 25-60-year-old possible participants were sent an email with an

explanation on the survey and the purpose behind it. These participants were found from the staff of government institutes including universities, ministries, employees of private organisations, members in social media groups and other contacts. Once receiving the positive feedback and affirmation of their willingness to participate voluntarily the google link was sent for them to participate.

Method of data analysis

Validity and reliability of the measures were evaluated. Principle component factor analysis was conducted using SPSS software. Factor analysis yielded two factors for fear of financial situation and uncertainty; these were named as fear of financial situation and fear of uncertainty. Factor analysis yielded two factors for resources available for spouses; these were named as family resources and cultural pressure. The fit measures were given in Table 1. Results of these tests were shown in Appendix 1 to 3. Moderation analysis was conducted using PROCESS programme developed by Hayes (2013). Indirect effects were assessed based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the size and significance of the effects.

Tables 1. Fit measures

	Cronbach's alpha	Explained variation	Total variation explained	Eigenvalue	AVE	Construct reliability
Fear of financial situation and uncertainty:						
Fear of financial situation	.958	47.47	74.78	7.695	.728	.956
Fear of uncertainty	.906	27.31		2.774	.698	.920
Adjustment of spouses	.800	83.349	83.349	1.667	.834	.909
Resources available for spouses:						
Family resources	.947	47.619	77.921	6.563	2.008	.946
Cultural pressure	.914	30.303		.714	.749	.923

V. RESULTS

Since fear of financial situation and fear of uncertainty yielded two factors and resources available for spouses yielded, we analysed four separate models. The results of these models are as follows.

Results relating to the fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources are shown in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, the effect of fear of financial situation (IV) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -.0249, p < .001$). The effect of family resources (M) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -.6438, p < .001$). The effect of interaction on adjustment of spouses is also significant ($B = .1327, p < .001$). Relationships between fear of financial situation (IV) and adjustment of spouses are significant for all low ($b = .2769, p < .001$), average ($b = .3667, p < .001$), and high ($b = .4564,$

$p < .001$) values of family resources (M). Overall, family resources (M) moderates the relationship between fear of financial situation (IV) and adjustment of spouses. Figure 2 shows this relationship figuratively.

Table 2. Fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources

	Adjustment of spouses (DV) B(SE)		
Fear of financial situation (IV)	-.0249(.1086)***		
Family resources (M)	-.6438(.1503)***		
Interaction (IVxM)	.1327(.0386)***		
R ²	.1591		
F (df1, df2)	18.6103(3, 295)***		
ΔR ²	.0337		
ΔF(df1, df2)	11.8372(1, 295)***		
Conditional effects:			
	-SD	Mean	+SD
Family resources (M)	2.2735	2.9501	3.6266
Effect (t)	.2769(5.6649)***	.3667(7.2432)***	.4564(7.1298)***

Notes: Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors = SE. Bootstrap sample size = 5000. *** $p < .001$ (two-tailed).

Figure 2. Moderation Graph- fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources

Results relating to the fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure are shown in Table 3. As shown in Table 3, the effect of fear of financial situation (IV) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -.3779, p < .05$). The effect of cultural pressure (M) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -.7468, p < .001$). The effect of interaction on adjustment of spouses is also significant ($B = .2120, p < .001$). Relationships between fear of financial situation (IV) and adjustment of spouses are significant for average ($b = .2827, p < .001$), and high ($b = .4196, p < .001$) values of cultural pressure (M). Overall, cultural pressure (M) moderates the relationship between fear of financial situation (IV) and adjustment of spouses. Figure 3 shows this relationship figuratively.

Table 3. Fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure

	Adjustment of spouses (DV) B(SE)		
Fear of financial situation (IV)	-.3779 (.1497)*		
Cultural pressure (M)	-.7468 (.1371)***		
Interaction (IVxM)	.2120 (.0369)***		
R ²	.1891		
F (df1, df2)	22.9282 (3, 295)***		
ΔR ²	.0908		
ΔF(df1, df2)	33.0175 (1, 295)***		
Conditional effects:			
	-SD	Mean	+SD
Cultural pressure (M)	2.4697	3.1157	3.7616
Effect (t)	.1457 (1.6620)	.2827(3.4860)***	.4196(5.1661)***

Notes: Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors = SE. Bootstrap sample size = 5000. * $p < .05$, *** $p < .001$ (two-tailed).

Figure 3. Moderation Graph- fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure

Results relating to the fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources are shown in Table 4. As shown in Table 4, the effect of fear of uncertainty (IV) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -1.2464, p < .001$). The effect of family resources (M) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -1.2464, p < .001$). The effect of interaction on adjustment of spouses is also significant ($B = .3016, p < .001$). Relationships between fear of uncertainty (IV) and adjustment of spouses are significant for all low ($b = -.5606, p < .001$) and average ($b = -.3565, p < .001$) values of family resources (M). Overall, family resources (M) moderates the relationship between fear of uncertainty (IV) and adjustment of spouses. Figure 4 shows this relationship figuratively.

Table 4. Fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources

	Adjustment of spouses (DV) B(SE)		
Fear of uncertainty (IV)	-1.2464 (.1338)***		
Family resources (M)	-.6110 (.1230)***		
Interaction (IVxM)	.3016 (.0327)***		
R ²	.2543		
F (df1, df2)	33.5309 (3, 295)***		
ΔR ²	.2148		
ΔF(df1, df2)	11.8372(1, 295)***		
Conditional effects:			
	-SD	Mean	+SD
Family resources (M)	2.2735	2.9501	3.6266
Effect (t)	-.5606 (-6.0664)***	-.3565 (-4.0129)***	-.1525(-1.6808)

Notes: Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors = SE. Bootstrap sample size = 5000. *** $p < .001$ (two-tailed).

Figure 4. Moderation Graph- fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources

Results relating to the fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure are shown in Table 5. As shown in Table 5, the effect of fear of uncertainty (IV) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -1.1135, p < .001$). The effect of cultural pressure (M) on adjustment of spouses is significant ($B = -.2921, p < .01$). The effect of interaction on adjustment of spouses is also significant ($B = .2322, p < .001$). Relationships between fear of uncertainty (IV) and adjustment of spouses are significant for all low ($b = -.5399, p < .001$), average ($b = -.3899, p < .001$), and high ($b = -.2399, p < .001$) values of cultural pressure (M). Overall, cultural pressure (M) moderates the relationship between fear of uncertainty (IV) and adjustment of spouses. Figure 5 shows this relationship figuratively.

Table 5. Fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure

	Adjustment of spouses (DV) B(SE)		
Fear of uncertainty (IV)	-1.1135 (.1466)***		
Cultural pressure (M)	-.2921 (.1034)**		
Interaction (IVxM)	.2322 (.0371)***		
R ²	.2207		
F (df1, df2)	27.8423 (3, 295)***		
ΔR ²	.1033		
ΔF(df1, df2)	39.1138 (1, 295)***		
Conditional effects:			
	-SD	Mean	+SD
Cultural pressure (M)	2.4697	3.1157	3.7616
Effect (t)	-.5399 (-8.0788)***	-.3899 (-7.3857)***	-.2399 (-5.0482)***

Notes: Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors = SE. Bootstrap sample size = 5000. ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$ (two-tailed).

Figure 5. Moderation Graph- fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure

VI. DISCUSSION

The COVID-19 pandemic has a persistent effect on all aspects of family life. As per Rolland (2020), coping with myriad COVID-19 uncertainties has created adjustment issues for many spouses and families. Inability to adjust may create negative consequences for individuals (e.g., depression, anxiety), the couple relationship (e.g. increased conflict, and aggression), and the couple's children (e.g., internalizing and externalizing behaviors) (Coop Gordon & Mitchell, 2020). So it is critical to understand the factors influencing adjustment of spouses during pandemic times as well as how they are moderated.

This research examined the well-being and relationship status of married couples during COVID-19 lockdown. The purpose of this paper was to investigate the relationship between fear of uncertainty and fear of financial situation on adjustment of spouses in Sri Lankan context. It also investigated the moderation effect of family resources and cultural pressure on the above relationships. This analysis of the recent COVID-19 lockdown in Sri Lanka will add significant input to the quarantine literature in terms of the functions of married couples and the way they adjust to bring harmony to their relationships. Even though the survey participants expressed moderate to high levels of uncertainty during the state-regulated lockdown, they claimed to experience high adjustment due to the support extended by families and their cultural beliefs. When compared with a study done by Brooks et al. (2020) on psychological effects of quarantine on couple and family relations the results of this study reaffirm the same.

The results of a previous study done by Holt-Lunstad et al. (2020) have pointed how effects of the lockdown is more complex for adult married couples than children and unmarried individuals. When in very close proximities the interpersonal needs become more complex in couples than individuals, which could be the reason for this difference. The current literature on COVID-19 has not shown how post-traumatic growth has influenced on positive individual change. Another study done by Nussbaumer-Streit et al. (2020, p5) states that, matrimonial “relations during lockdown appeared more harmonious when there were no children in the household, and moderation analyses indicated that COVID-related employment variables such as telecommuting predicted successful couple functioning in different ways depending on parental status”.

Since fear of uncertainty plays a major role in all adjustment processes of humans including family, work, cultural adjustment, the findings of research was in line with many past research (Sterle, Vervoort, & Verhofstadt, 2018). However, this relationship is influenced by the support or resistance by external environment. This research found out that cultural pressure plays a key moderation role in the relationships. This is inline with many recent findings on the similar research (Gudmundsdottir, Gudlaugsson, Adalsteinsson, 2019; Ritu, Pratyush & Jighyasu, 2012; Wilson, 2011). As per a study carried out on European spouses, Gudmundsdottir, Gudlaugsson, Adalsteinsson (2019) revealed that there is a significant

relationship between adjustment and emotional support as well as satisfaction with life. External emotional support is mainly depended on cultural aspects. Wilson (2011) found out that spousal adjustment mainly depends on support factors related to culture. The research carried out in India by Ritu, Pratyush, and Jighyasu (2012) found that cultural, organizational and family support plays a key role in spouse adjustment.

Family resources are the means that can be used by the family to cope with difficult situations; these include social, cultural, religious, economic and medical resources. These become much more important in difficult times such as pandemic where uncertainties and restrictions are high. It was found that family support system and family resources promote FQOL (Family Quality of Life) thereby family satisfaction (Zen et. Al., 2020). When financial situation uncertainties are high, family resources tend to partially replenish the negative aspects such as children's mental health and psychological distress Berger & Font, 2015). Research outcomes investigating moderation effect of family resources on family uncertainties are rare but the outcomes of similar research gives credence to the fact that the positive moderation effect actually exists.

CONCLUSION

We are living in a challenging and an uncertain time. COVID-19 which was declared as a global crisis which has brought a significant influence on the lives of all humans and Sri Lankans are no different. This pandemic has created a catastrophe in health and economic stability of Sri Lanka as well as the well being of families. This study investigated the individual and relational well-being of married couples who were confined during the months of state-regulated lockdown during the COVID-19 outbreak in Sri Lanka.

The specified main objectives this study was to identify whether individuals suffer from fears on financial situation and uncertainty, to analyse the level of adjustment of spouses, to investigate the resources available for spouses, and to understand whether resource availability moderates the relationship between individuals' fears on financial situation/uncertainty and the level of adjustment of spouses.

A conceptual model was developed and variables such as uncertainty, financial situation and resources available for spouses were reviewed in relation to the adjustment of spouses. Four hypotheses were established which were H1: Uncertainty influences the adjustment of spouses, H2: Financial situation of spouses influences the adjustment of spouses, H3: Resources available for spouses moderates the relationship between uncertainty and the adjustment of spouses and H4: Resources available for spouses moderates the relationship between financial situation and the adjustment of spouses.

With a detailed literature review, it was established that the resources available for married spouses that affect their adjustment during COVID-19 includes family resources and cultural beliefs. The methodology for data collection was done through a survey which was distributed among males and females

of the age 25 – 60 residing mostly in in or outside the Western Province. The questionnaire had 82 questions and the data were collected from 301 respondents.

Since fear of financial situation and fear of uncertainty yielded two factors and resources available for spouses yielded, the study analysed four separate models. Results relating to the fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources conclude that family resources moderates, the relationship between fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses. Results relating to the fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure conclude that cultural pressure moderates, the relationship between fear of financial situation and adjustment of spouses. Results relating to the fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by family resources conclude that family resources moderates, the relationship between fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses. Results relating to the fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses moderated by cultural pressure conclude that cultural pressure moderates, the relationship between fear of uncertainty and adjustment of spouses.

From the time the first COVID-19 patient was announced the Ministry of Health and the National Operation Centre for Prevention of COVID-19 Outbreak kept on providing continuous updates and statistics on the pandemic via all media platforms. The study results also confirmed how this contributed to the uncertainty among married couples. Most married couples who were locked down in their homes engage in these updates and tend to panic about the financial situations they are in. As the study concluded the cultural beliefs and the support extended from the families contributed to adjustment of Sri Lankan spouses who managed to stay strong during the global crisis due to that.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This research study can identify a few limitations. Even if the target was to get an equal participation from both genders it turned out that majority of the participants were women. Another limitation is the language of the survey and the mode used, which was online. Having the survey only in the English language may have restricted participants who may be only versatile in a local language and the couples who do not use computers or have internet on their mobile phone devices may have been eliminated. The survey questionnaire tried to obtain the answers to the adjustment of spouses but there was a limitation in obtaining additional information from the participants, like the methods used to cope with economic challenges and changes in their marital relationships. The survey questionnaire was distributed during a period where it was a partial lockdown. This was in between two country-wide lockdowns. Many couples may have remembered the former lockdown but would have assumed situation of the country to get better. Thus, without anticipating another lockdown they may have been biased in their answers to sound more positive. The survey was done prior to the third wave of COVID-19 and the most severe death rates and infected

numbers being announced and therefore, the results of financial situation and uncertainty may be worse now than the time of the survey. As seen in many studies the validity of answers may be a limitation in a general online survey. The chosen number in the sample may have a limitation of representing all the married couples of Sri Lanka.

Future research may include replicating the same study with a more diverse sample. Additionally a Qualitative research can also be done in future with the use of interviewing couples and doing a few case study analyses. Future researchers can conduct a follow-up study to identify long-term effects of COVID-19 on Sri Lankan married couples. With the coming months and the impact of COVID-19 broadens future researches can identify how the pandemic affects the relationships of married couples and find whether the short-term changes found in this study remains the same or changes. Further studies can be done to identify resolutions these couples have taken to rectify the adjustments and how they would overcome the barriers in the long run.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Fear of financial situation and uncertainty

Question	Fear of financial situation	Uncertainty
My spouse's attempt to control my spending money causes disagreement.	.764	
For me, it has been difficult to adjust to the economic needs of my spouse	.813	
I feel that if my spouse had a better education we would have more money	.825	
Fights over money often occur	.882	
My spouse and I find it difficult to communicate when expressing views on monetary needs	.903	
Disagreements over money offer an easy way to release hostility	.923	
Disagreements over what to spend money on have occurred in my marriage	.800	
My spouse and I have disagreements over who will handle the family money	.901	
My spouse and I disagree about which bills need to be paid at the first of the month	.798	
I consider budgeting money carefully to be important		.855
I would respect my spouse's occupation if he did not earn an average salary		.880
My spouse's spending habits are agreeable with me and efficient		.798
I feel financially capable to take care of myself in cases of crisis		.873
I feel that education guarantees a stable income		.765
Eigenvalue	7.695	2.774
Explained variation (rotation sum of squared Loadings)	47.47	27.31
Cronbach's alpha	.958	.906
AVE	.728	.698
Construct reliability	.956	.920

Appendix 2. Adjustment of spouses

Question	Adjustment
Handling Family Finances	.913
Matters of Recreation	.913
Eigenvalue	1.667
Explained variation (rotation sum of squared Loadings)	83.349
Cronbach's alpha	.800
AVE	.834
Construct reliability	.909

Appendix 3. Resources available for spouses

Question	Family resources	Cultural pressure
I feel comfortable around my in-laws	.835	
Sharing of responsibility and respect has been an important occurrence in my marriage	.892	
My in-laws have been pleased and supportive of my marriage	.877	
Religion plays an important part in my life	.834	
My spouse and I hold the same religious convictions	.845	
Religion was important to me as I was growing up	.829	
I am self-confident about my abilities as a parent	.801	
Children and the thought of-children make me feel tied down		.799
The pressure to have children-has been a disagreeable aspect of my marriage		.881
I feel that my spouse has only a few of the qualities I wanted in a mate		.907
Our standard of living appears to be below that of our friends		.872
Eigenvalue	6.563	2.008
Explained variation (rotation sum of squared Loadings)	47.619	30.303
Cronbach's alpha	.947	.914
AVE	.714	.749
Construct reliability	.946	.923